

DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' PROFESSIONAL COMMUNICATION

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Abstract. This article discusses the issues of training specialists in the conditions of social partnership of higher professional education with the production environment. The authors of the article describe the employer's ability to assess potential human resources at the early stages of professional training. The author highlight the professional, organizational and managerial qualities of students that are in demand by industry employers today.

Keywords: training of specialists, professional education, professional competence, professional activity, component, level of formation.

INTRODUCTION

The social and cultural changes taking place in the society ensured that the educational system acquired a new content in an evolutionary way, and educational values were formed that reflect advanced ideas. Universal, spiritual-ethical, professional values are significant in that they serve to educate the personality of the pedagogue, increase his dignity, and also help to form the skills of social activity. Therefore, the need to raise a competent person and qualified specialist becomes more urgent in the current conditions where new social relations are being decided in the developing world.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Development of new approaches to pedagogical education, such as democratization, humanization, fundamentalization (basic) of the content of training of specialists of Uzbekistan's higher education, ensuring the integrity of educational

programs, the scope of ideology, elimination of influence, focus on universal values, creation of conditions for personal and professional development instead of formation ideology. General changes were made according to the tradition [1]. In general, pedagogic education reform was carried out based on three concepts, and each of them included working on a specific/concrete aspect of the innovative change process.

Modern innovative directions of pedagogical education include 1) development of own innovation theory; 2) person-oriented education;

3) a person-oriented-activity-based paradigm in the professional training/education of a pedagogue; 4) it is possible to distinguish the development of the organizational-structural model of education, the creation of a multi-level educational system.

1) Over the past decades, K. Angelovski, M.V. Klarin, V.Ya. Lyaudis, M.M. Potashnik, T.I. Shamova, O.T. Homericky, N.R. Yusufbekova, V.I. Zhuravlev, V.I. In the work of scientists like Zagvyazinsky, the first concept - the concept of pedagogical innovation is being actively developed [2].

In the process of receiving (providing) education at the higher education institution, identifying the specific features of the pedagogical professionalism of the future teacher and the opportunities for the formation and development of his innovative potential is provided by a number of higher education concepts (psycho-pedagogy, creative pedagogy, etc.). In the framework of our research work, the experience of creative activity serves as a priority direction of professional training (education) of students of a higher educational institution and one of the components of the content of their professional competence.

2) The second concept of person-oriented education is based on cultural-historical and activity-based approaches (J.I. Vygotsky, A.A. Leontev, D.B. Elkonin. E.V. Ilenkov, V.V. Davidov, G.P. Shchedrovitsky, A.G. Asmolov) and to date its general methodological development scientists: V.V. Serikov, V.G.

Zuckerman, V.P. Zinchenko, J.H. Kulikova is; with this problem at the organizational-management level, M.N. Kostikova, V.A. Bolotovs are engaged.

The essence and meaning of the person-oriented concept can be expressed by the following interrelated (related) main points (theses). The main thesis is related to rethinking the role and place of science-based education/training in pedagogic education: mastering (mastering) the science of teaching loses its status as a central task and becomes a tool for realizing the student's goals, a means of his development. Another idea of this concept is related to the construction of educational forms that are connected to the educational process (to the educational activity itself) and to its understanding (understanding) and the formation of the future teacher's personal pedagogical point of view. The main rules of this approach are defined in the following sequence: the person is the main value for himself and "others", education is the change of the person, which is carried out in the course of the integrated pedagogical process of higher education; the primary outcome of such education is not knowledge, skills, and abilities, but personal productivity focused on personal growth, empathic/compassionate interaction, and a high level of social engagement.

Due to natural and social reasons, the adolescent age of students is primarily sensitive to the rapid formation of self-awareness for goal-oriented self-determination in personal-social roles. In this regard, in the process of higher education, not only the "building up" of new knowledge and social experience takes place, but also its personal formation - self-education in accordance with one's own life strategy. In order to realize his life prospects, a person consciously "continues to build himself", and for this he uses the opportunities of the educational process. Another thesis of the concept is related to finding ways to eliminate the conflict between the student's educational activity and the realization of his personal pedagogical point of view (pedagogical credo) and the formation of his personal pedagogical point of view (position): the resolution of this conflict requires reflection (reflection on actions/thoughts formation of various forms, the educational

process (the educational activity itself) and its understanding and research work will be possible through the construction of educational forms.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

First, you need to define the term “professional competence”. This term is often found in foreign literature. Thus, the Oxford English Dictionary gives the following definition of this concept: “competence” – the ability to do something successfully or efficiently (the ability to do something successfully or efficiently) [1]. Australian scientist T. Hoffman defines the concept of “competence” as visible and fixed results of activity, as certain standards for performing certain types of work, as personal properties that determine the effectiveness of a particular activity [3]. According to the definition of E.F. Zeer and E.E. Symanyuk, “competence” is the integrative integrity and effectiveness of knowledge, skills and abilities in general [4]. S.Sh. Chernova denotes the term “competence” as a personality characteristic, meaning the possession of a set of certain competencies [2].

On the basis of certain features, various approaches to the typology of communications are distinguished.

1. According to the scale of the process and the mass nature of the persons involved in it, mass, medium-level, local, intragroup, intergroup, interpersonal, intrapersonal communications are determined.

2. According to the method of establishing and maintaining contact, direct (direct) and indirect (remote) communications are distinguished.

3. According to the initiative of communicators, communications are divided into active and passive.

4. According to the degree of organization, communications are random and non-random (organized).

5. Depending on the direction of the flow of information, communications are divided into horizontal, which are carried out between members of the group with equal status, and vertical, occurring between the subjects of communication that are in subordinate relations. Vertical communications are descending (a

communication flow moving from a higher level in a group or organization to a lower level) and ascending (information is sent from a lower to a higher level and is used for feedback from subordinates to the manager in order to inform about performance and current issues).

6. Depending on the sign systems used, verbal (speech) and non-verbal (non-speech) communications are distinguished, interconnected and complementing each other, with the help of which information becomes multifaceted, the speech impact of communicators is strengthened or weakened, the intentions of communication participants are revealed [2].

The classical communication paradigm, proposed by the American political scientist Harold Lasswell in 1948, is based on a consistent series of questions regarding the transfer of information: who transmitted, what transmitted, through what channel, to whom and with what result (what effect does it cause).

An important goal and main function of modern communication is to unite people on the basis of common access to the necessary information. In this case, not only information is transmitted in one direction or one-sided influence is exerted on the communicants, but their interaction is also activated.

For example, a discussion belongs to communicative-dialogue technologies. As an object of discussion, specially formulated problems, as well as situations of interpersonal and professional relations of participants, can act. A group discussion activates the motivation of students in solving the problems discussed, contributes to their subsequent search activity, the clarification of each participant's own point of view, the development of initiative, communication skills.

During the role-playing game, the student receives answers to the questions: why (motive) and why (goal) it is necessary to act in a given situation. Speech communication, including verbal and non-verbal means, in the game is purposeful and mandatory in order to stimulate creative thinking, variability of speech activity, initiative in solving problem situations.

The identification of criterion indicators of motivational and organizational-managerial components of professional competence contributed to the selection of methods for monitoring the degree of their formation, which are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Structural components of professional competence of students and methods of their diagnosis

Component/Criterion	Index	Methods and techniques
Motivational	- motivation to achieve success/avoid failure;	method “Determining a person’s focus on achieving success/avoiding failure” (A.A. Rean);
	- motivation for educational activities;	methodology “Studying motivation for studying at a university” (T.I. Ilyina);
	- degree of satisfaction with the profession;	method “Studying the attractiveness factor of a profession” (V.Ya Yadov);
	- interest in research activities and obtaining the product of research activities in the form of rationalization proposals	survey;
Organizational and managerial	- reflective - strength of will - activity;	“Personality Differential” technique, adapted by employees of the Psychoneurological Institute named after. V.M. Bekhterev;
	- leadership skills;	methodology “Leadership Potential” (V.V. Boyko);
	- communication skills; - organizational qualities.	methodology “Communicative and organizational tendencies” (V.V. Sinyavsky, B.A. Fedorishin)

We assessed the motivational component according to the motivational criterion, which in our study is presented as a set of the following indicators: motivation to achieve success/avoid failure; motivation for professional activity; degree of satisfaction with the profession; interest in research activities and obtaining the product of research activities in the form of rationalization proposals.

According to the results of a study using the method of “Determining a person’s focus on achieving success/avoiding failure” (A.A. Rean), 47.5% of

students showed a focus on “achieving success.” This orientation refers to positive motivation. Thus, 47.5% of the surveyed students, setting a goal, strive to achieve it, create it, and get down to business with confidence in a positive result. The need to achieve high results and, as a consequence of this, high self-esteem underlies such positive activity. At the same time, 52.5% of the students surveyed show the motivation of “avoiding failure,” which refers to negative motivation. According to this motivation, human activity is associated with negative expectations. The expectation of failure, reproach, fear of possible failure makes them think not about how to achieve success, but about how to avoid it. Characterized by increased anxiety, they tend to lack self-confidence.

In terms of leadership qualities, students were assessed based on the “Leadership Potential” methodology (V.V. Boyko [6]). As a result of the analysis of the study, it can be noted that 7.5% of the surveyed students showed high leadership qualities, leadership qualities were expressed on average in 72.5% of the surveyed students, and 20% of the surveyed students showed a low level of expression of leadership qualities. In this regard, only 7.5% of students have pronounced “manager” competencies, which involve the ability to plan, organize, control, motivate, make decisions, and show flexibility in choosing a management style depending on the parameters of the situation.

Table 2

The structure of the organizational and managerial criterion for the formation of professional competence of students

Criterion	Indicators and their content
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Organizational and managerial	<p>Leadership qualities - the ability to plan, organize, control, motivate, make decisions, and show flexibility in choosing a management style depending on the parameters of the situation.</p> <p>Communication skills - the ability to establish new contacts, speak in front of an audience, the need for communication.</p> <p>Organizational qualities – the ability to defend one’s own point of view and make independent decisions.</p> <p>Reflexive – the ability to consciously control the results of one’s activities and personal achievements determines the level of development of self-esteem, understanding of one’s own significance for other people, responsibility for the results of one’s activities, self-realization in the process of professional activity.</p> <p>Willpower – self-control, self-confidence, a tendency to independence, self-reliance in difficult situations.</p> <p>Activity – determination of dominance-submission status, level of activity, avoidance of responsibility.</p>
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The results of the study using the “Communicative and Organizational Abilities” method developed by V.V. Sinyavsky and B.A. Fedorishin [5], showed that 20% of the surveyed students showed a high level of communicative qualities, 35% of respondents showed an average level and 45% of the surveyed students had a low level of communicative qualities. The level of organizational skills, namely the ability to defend one’s own point of view and make an independent decision, is presented as follows: 22.5% of students have a high level, 37.5% of students showed an average level and 40% of students surveyed have a low level. level of organizational skills. In connection with the data obtained, we can conclude that students do not strive to communicate, feel constrained in the new environment of studying at a university, experience difficulties in establishing contacts with new people and when speaking in front of an audience, and are poorly oriented in an unfamiliar situation; in many matters they prefer to avoid making independent decisions. However, despite this, they feel the need for communication, defending their opinion and ensuring that it is accepted by their comrades, they are persistent in activities that attract them, but they are not distinguished by high emotional stability.

Thus, an analysis of the level of formation of the main components of professional competence of students of four groups at the ascertaining stage showed

that among the students surveyed, “obtaining a diploma” is of paramount importance, and such a motive as “mastering a profession” occupies the last place. At the same time, the majority of students demonstrate a high need to achieve high results and, based on this, have a high level of self-esteem. In this regard, respondents are characterized by self-confidence, self-confidence, initiative and activity. However, about a third of the students surveyed are not confident in their abilities and are characterized by increased anxiety, which, however, can be combined with a very responsible attitude to business. They try to avoid responsible tasks, and when such a need arises, their situational anxiety increases under the influence of negative expectations.

CONCLUSION

The conducted research allowed us to conclude that the level of formation of the motivational and organizational-managerial components of the professional competence of students studying does not meet the requirements of the heads of leading enterprises, as well as the requirements of recruitment agencies for a university graduate. which determines the feasibility of introducing new organizational and pedagogical conditions that increase the efficiency of specialist training.

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